

Facilitation Guide

New Mexico Early Career Leadership Workshop

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Agenda

1. Workshop Overview

- a) Experiential learning: People retain information and skills more by doing than through lecture.
- b) Explore: How can effective facilitation make you more effective as a researcher, teacher, or community leader?

2. Facilitation Technique #1: Storyboarding/Workshop/Vision Methods

Discussion question: Imagine, five years from now, New Mexico is recognized as having the nation's BEST model for integrated STEM education, from K-12 into higher education. What does New Mexico's STEM environment look like? What bold innovations played into our success?

3. Facilitation Technique #2: Nominal Group Technique

Discussion question: Imagine that, through innovative collaboration between New Mexico's universities and its national laboratories, the state has become a global leader in both diversified energy production and long-term storage. What **bold steps** did we take to enable that collaboration?

4. Facilitation Technique #3: Pyramid Conversations

Discussion question: The scientific community is in the business of learning new information, whether it be on vaccine efficacy, climate change, or water management. Sometime the public doesn't have confidence in new data or take research seriously. When we need the public to take action on research finding, what are the three biggest challenges?

5. Debrief

- a) Powerful Questions
- b) Facilitation Tips
- c) Questions

Storyboarding

Storyboarding¹ provides a way to generate and arrange ideas. It gets its name from the Disney Corporation using the process to develop “story boards” for feature length cartoons. This facilitation technique is also known as **Affinity Diagramming**.

STEP ONE: Meeting Preparation

Storyboarding works best with very small groups of 3 or 4 people. If your group consists of more people, divide the group into groups of 3 or 4.

The room should be set up so that each small group has a place to meet. Storyboarding is a relatively quiet process and many groups can meet in the same large space. Each group needs a table, part of a wall to place their post their ideas, a supply of post-it notes (at least 3” x 3”) and a water-based marker for each person.

STEP TWO: Conducting the Meeting

The best way to describe the process is to demo it. If you are working with a large group, divide it into small groups. You might have them count off, or allow them to select the question they wish to work on (if there are different questions), or assign them to groups according to some criteria.

Do a quick demo:

1. Invite **one** of the small groups into the center of the room.
2. Pass out the supplies—each person gets post-it notes and a marker.
3. Ask them the key question and instruct them to write down as many responses to the question as they can think of, one response for each post-it note.
4. After about two or three minutes of work, ask one of the participants for one of their items. Read off the item and ask whether any of the other people have a similar item. Cluster similar responses together on the flipchart or wall. Read off one item for each person, cluster similar responses as you go, and then instruct them to continue clustering items on their own.

Repeat the process with the full group:

1. Pass out supplies to each of the small groups (each person gets post-it notes and a marker) and instruct them to do the following: (It is helpful if these steps are listed on a flipchart.)
2. Write down your responses to the question, one item per note.
3. After about five minutes, compare and cluster items.
4. Develop categories based on the clusters and the single items.

If a number of groups are working on the same item, it is productive to ask everyone to walk around the room and read the categories created by each of the small groups. You can then facilitate a discussion where people report what seem to be common categories that can be found in the work of most of the groups, what surprised them, what they believe is missing.

¹ *A Facilitator’s Manual*, Carl M. Moore

Workshop Method

The Workshop Method² is a way to both generate and develop ideas. It also gradually builds mutual understanding and consensus across the group in selecting ideas for implementation. The approach allows participants to integrate their thinking and take responsibility for their results. The original method was created by The Institute of Cultural Affairs. The following is a variation on this method.

STEP ONE: Meeting Preparation

Consistent with the purpose (desired outcomes) of the meeting, format a question that will focus the participants on creative ideas to address the issue.

You will also need to prepare the materials the participants will use during their discussions. They will be using:

- Large cards (approximately 8" x 6") which can be purchased as self-stick post it notes or by cutting copy paper in half
- Black markers
- Painter's tape (if you are using copy paper as cards)
- Wall space large enough to post the cards and rearrange them as needed

Create the instructions on large cards to show participants a model for how to use the cards during the meeting. These include:

You will post these cards in a column on the wall space where you will be posting the participants' cards.

STEP TWO: Conducting the Meeting

Set the stage for the meeting by clearly explaining the topic and goal of the meeting and its importance to the group. Next, highlight the question to be addressed (e.g., What are practical ways to build effective teamwork) and outline the process and the timeline for each part. You may want to ask one or two warm-up questions to start people thinking about their experience with this topic (e.g., What is the most effective team you have been part of and what is one thing that worked well in this team?)

The discussion will proceed in a series of rounds. The number of rounds depends on the time allotted for the discussion and the number of participants. You can also adjust the number of ideas to be submitted by both individuals and sub-groups for consideration given the time allowed. The following is an

² Adapted from *Technology of Participation: Group Facilitation Methods*, The Institute of Cultural Affairs

example.

Round 1: Individuals (approximately 5 minutes). Individuals record 5-6 initial ideas that answer the question, each idea on a separate card, and then select their 3 clearest and best ideas.

Round 2: Sub-groups of 3-5 (approximately 20-40 minutes). Each sub-group reviews each individual's 3 ideas and comes to consensus on 5-7 clearest and best ideas to share with the full group. They should rewrite these ideas as they are probably the result of combining similar ideas or building on ideas. However, the resulting 5-7 ideas should still be expressed succinctly and clearly.

At this point you could combine 2 sub-groups and repeat the process, or you could move to having the sub-groups report out.

Round 3: Full-group reports (approximately 45 minutes). Ask the first sub-group to report out and post their 5-7 ideas, one idea at a time. Ask subsequent groups to do the same, but to refrain from posting duplicate ideas. All unique ideas should be posted.

Round 4: Clarify and select ideas (approximately 30-45 minutes). Lead the full group in a discussion to flesh out, clarify, combine, build on, advocate for the ideas. This may lead to clustering of ideas that create an integrated idea.

Debrief the meeting: At the conclusion of the final round, summarize the key ideas and move onto next steps such as a deeper exploration, prioritization of the ideas, selection of the top idea(s), or action planning for implementation.

Nominal Group Technique

Nominal Group Technique,³ or NGT, provides a way to generate ideas and to organize those ideas into a prioritized list. It is extremely useful when the time for a meeting is limited, but it is important that all ideas of a group are heard.

STEP ONE: Meeting Preparation

NGT works best with small groups of 5-9. If your group consists of more people, plan to divide the group in a random way into smaller groups. A facilitator will be needed for each group, so part of your meeting preparation will be recruiting and training enough facilitators for each small group.

The room(s) should be set up so that each small group has a place to gather. Because each group will be talking, noise may be a factor to deal with if all the groups are in one room. Therefore, think about the location for the meeting ahead of time. If possible, allow for one large room for the group to gather initially and then break out into smaller, separate rooms. Each group facilitator will need: a flipchart, assorted colors of water-based markers, drafting/masking tape, strips of dots, and enough pencils and paper for each person in the group.

For NGT to be successful, it is important that the meeting organizers, together with the meeting facilitator, discuss what question the group will be asked to consider. Keeping in mind what the meeting is expected to accomplish, design a question that is simply stated and allows for creativity of ideas, but also is specific enough so everyone's thoughts are channeled in the same direction. For example, a poor NGT question would be:

“What can you as an individual and we as a community do to ensure funding support for public education both in the long-term and short-term?”

This is a poor question because it is too complex and requires responses to be given such that it would be difficult to determine for which part of the question ideas were given.

A better question would be:

“What can be done to ensure funding support for public education?”

STEP TWO: Preparing the Group

Ideally, a chairperson will clarify the purpose of the meeting, the context for the meeting (how this meeting fits into the history of the group and their ongoing work) and the facilitator's role. You should be prepared to describe your role if it is not done by someone else.

You should outline the steps of the NGT. You might say something like this.

“Given the session's purpose, we as a group will consider the following question (read the question which has been previously written on a flipchart.)

“First, everyone will work silently and independently for four minutes. You should take time to

³ *A Facilitator's Manual*, Carl M. Moore

jot down all of your responses to the question.

“Next, I will go around the circle, calling upon you one at a time so you can give one of your ideas (responses). I will write them down on flipcharts. I will go around the group several times until I get down most of your ideas.

“After I have recorded your ideas, we will revisit each one to make certain that its meaning is clear to everyone in the group.

“The final step will be a voting procedure whereby you will identify what you believe are the best responses to the question.”

Then ask the group, “Do these steps appear to be a reasonable way to generate ideas?”

STEP THREE: The Actual Process

First: Ask the question. Pass out sheets of paper with the question at the top of the page. Tell the group,

“For the next four minutes, please work silently and independently. Please write down your ideas. The paper will not be collected.”

If anyone does start to talk or to do anything else that is likely to be disruptive to the others in the group, remind them:

“This is the time for each of you to do your own work. You will get a chance to talk to the other members of the group in just a moment.”

During the time that the group is working silently, tear off masking tape for hanging flipcharts and prepare strips of “dots” for the voting. You will need one strip of dots for each participant.

Second: Collect ideas. After the group has finished silently writing, begin the collection of ideas. You might begin by saying something like:

“I want to go around the table and collect one idea at a time from each of you. I will call upon each of you more than once, so you will have a chance to contribute at least a few of your ideas.

“Listen to what others in the group say to make certain that you do not give me exactly the same idea. I do not need to write down an idea more than once. Another reason to listen is because someone may say something that causes you to remember something that should be contributed and you might not have thought about it had you not listened.

“You may pass at any time if you do not have an item to contribute when I call on you. I will call on you again when I come back to you the next time.”

As an item is given to you, record it on the flipchart. Write down *exactly* what they say. Do not ask them to say it in a few words (unless it is extremely long). Resist the temptation to say, “Don’t you really mean” and then provide your idea. It is very important that the group feel that it is their list, and the most important thing that can be done to assure they believe that the list is theirs is to use their language.

Number each item in consecutive order. Start numbering about (6) inches from the left edge of the page, to allow room for the voting.

Alternate the colors of each item. That will enhance the readability of the items.

Speed is the most important factor in getting down the items. Do not belabor your handwriting or worry about your spelling. Get the items down quickly.

You should collect all of their items, if possible. But there is a point of diminishing return if the list gets too long. Experience suggests that a list of 20-30 will include almost all of a group's important items. If it is a very large group, 12 or more, tell them that you are going to go around the group two times. That will encourage them to give you their best item. After two passes, you can ask if there are any more items that have to be on the list. If it is a very, very large group, 25 or more, and you were not able to do the best thing, which would have been to break them up into more than one group, you should not try to go around the group more than once.

Third: Clarify ideas. Once all of the ideas have been collected, and are written down on sheets in front of the group, the task is to clarify the meaning of the ideas. The way to do this is to read each of them, in order, and ask if the meaning of the item is clear. If it is, if there are no comments about the meaning of the item, move on to the next one. Do that until you work your way through the entire list. You need to be clear with the group that this is not an occasion to argue about the worth of an item. They will have an opportunity in the next stage, with their vote, to indicate which items they believe are most important.

There are occasions when it is important for the group to argue about the worth of the items on the list, but only if they have allocated sufficient time to do that. Your job as facilitator will be to keep the group to the time they have allocated.

One suggestion for how to allocate time is to allow 15 minutes for voting and to divide the remaining time by the number of items. For example, if you have an hour left at the point when you are about to begin discussing the items, that will give you 45 minutes for the discussion. If you have 20 items to consider, you might announce to the group that they have a little over two minutes to discuss each item.

It is often the case that someone will try and reduce the complexity of the list by grouping items in broad categories. Your rule should be to consider a request only if the items are identical. Someone gave you the item with the knowledge they were only to contribute it, if it was different. Sometimes group discussion can determine that two (or even more) items mean the same thing, and you should do something about that, such as create a single item and eliminate the duplicates. But make changes in the list very cautiously and with respect for the original language. Check with the group. Ask them, "Do items 11 and 18 mean exactly the same thing?" If not, allow them to stay in the original form.

Fourth: Vote. Once the group is clear about the meaning of the items, they can vote to determine which are the most important items. Voting will allow the group to select those items which are the most important to them.

Pass out the appropriate number of colored dots to each person using the following ratios: 15 ideas = 3 votes; 15-30 ideas = 5 votes; >30 ideas = 7, and then instruct them as follows:

Ask them to take four to five minutes to decide privately the ideas they want to emphasize and to write the number of the idea on a dot (helps them make their own individual choice and not be influenced by others).

Once *everyone* has determined their favorite ideas and written the numbers on the dots, have everyone get up, go to the sheets posted on the wall, and place their dots by the appropriate item.

This will allow for a visual representation of the group's preferences. The items with the most dots next to them will be the most important items to the group.

If the small group is going to reconvene in a larger group, ask for a volunteer from the group to report the "top" items to the larger group.

At this point, the actual Nominal Group Technique process is finished. Whoever is in charge of the meeting should take over and discuss the next steps with everyone.

Pyramid Conversation

Pyramid Conversation⁴ surfaces the best ideas in a group and fosters everyone's commitment to a final choice very efficiently. It draws on the research described in *Blink*, that we often know more on an unconscious level than a conscious one and in *The Wisdom of Groups*, that all of us are smarter than any one of us. It requires participants to work quickly without a lot of self-censoring and analysis. It requires equal and simultaneous input from everyone. It gradually builds mutual understanding and consensus across the group.

STEP ONE: Meeting Preparation

Consistent with the purpose (desired outcomes) of the meeting, format a question that will elicit key variables as a list of three, for example:

- What are the three biggest challenges we face in (your specific situation)?
- What are the three most important things we need to do immediately to address (your specific situation)?
- What are the three key messages we need to communicate about (your specific situation)?

STEP TWO: Conducting the Meeting

Describe the purpose: Explain that the goal of this activity is to access the group's best and most spontaneous thinking on the issue. Indicate that there is significant research that suggests that by not censoring our first thoughts and by using the collective wisdom of the group, we can improve the quality of our decisions.

Round 1: Singles (up to 3 minutes). Show the prepared question and ask each participant to write down his/her three answers to the question. Stress that they should work quickly and not censor their first thoughts. Reinforce that there is no priority to the list, each item has equal value. Watch the group and move to the second round as soon as possible.

Round 2: Pairs (up to 5 minutes). Ask each participant to turn to another and form a pair. Indicate that they should quickly share their three ideas with each other and develop one list of three that both of them can agree to. Advise them that they can do this any way that works for them—take one from one list and two from the other, take all three items from one list, or throw out all the initial ideas and come up with three new ones—as long as they agree with the new list. Stress that they have only 5 minutes to come to consensus and keep up the pressure to conform to the timeframe by giving a 2 minute and 1 minute warning.

⁴ *Collaboration Tools*, Barbara Simonetti

Round 3: Fours (up to 8 minutes). Ask the pairs to turn to another pair and form a foursome. Remind them to take the time to position themselves so that everyone has eye contact with everyone else. Ask each pair to share only the list of three that they have both just agreed to, and then, arrive at a new list of three that all four can agree to. Announce the timing is 5 minutes and quietly extend the time up to 8 minutes if needed. Circulate around the room and help keep the groups on task and on time.

Listen for groups that are finishing early.

Round 4: Eights (up to 10 minutes). As soon as two groups have finished the task, invite them to form a group of eight, and again, share the list of three from the last round and arrive at a new list of three that all eight can agree to. Remind them to take the time to form their chairs into a circle so each participant has an equal position for joining the conversation. Announce the timing is 5 minutes and quietly extend the time up to 10 minutes if needed.

NOTE: You can repeat the process of combining groups until you only have 3 to 5 groups left. If you go beyond groups of 16, you can invite the two groups of eight to appoint four representatives to negotiate for the rest of the group. Groups over 16 will need a 10 minute round.

Debrief the Meeting

At the conclusion of the final round, ask the groups to record their final list of three on a flipchart and post them where everyone can see the lists simultaneously. Review the charts looking for similar items. Most often at least two of the three items will appear on most if not all of the charts. Check assumptions about what a group meant by an item and if it is similar to another group's meaning. Highlight or circle the most frequently mentioned items. The final list does not need to be limited to three items. It can include all the items from the groups' lists with those items listed most frequently at the top. Summarize the key items and move onto next steps such as a deeper exploration of the items or action planning for implementation.

Powerful Conversations

Why Questions?⁵ Powerful conversations are based on powerful questions. Questions open imaginations and then open doors to action. They invite creativity and innovation. They reinforce a “can-do” culture.

A meeting based on questions lead to conversations that generate new ideas, capture creative insights, and formulate needed change. Curiosity leads to knowledge.

Meetings allow people to connect through conversation and then to unite in committed action if the questions are thought-provoking, invite possibilities, and generate energy. Therefore the quality of the questions matter. The following will help you build questions that lead to results.

Dimensions of Powerful Questions:

- *Construction*—The words you use can make a question more or less powerful. Although yes/no questions (i.e., which) and questions that generate factual information (i.e., who, when, where) can be useful, more powerful questions stimulate reflection and surfaces underlying assumptions (i.e., what, how, why).

Compare: Was that decision right or wrong? versus What does it mean to be ethical?

- *Scope*—For most organizations, it is important to consider broader and larger aspects of the system that is being explored. However, it is also important to keep people focused within a realistic boundary so they feel they have the capacity to influence events.

Consider: How can we be more collaborative as manager and direct report? as a work team? with our organizational partners?

- *Assumptions*—Each question should be reviewed to determine if there are underlying beliefs inherent in the way the question is formed that would be counter-productive to the conversation.

Compare: What did we do wrong? versus What can we learn from this situation?

⁵ *The Art of Powerful Questions*, Eric E. Vogt, Juanita Brown, and David Isaacs

Creating Questions

The following questions will help you gain experience in crafting powerful questions. These questions are adapted from the work of Sally Ann Roth of the Public Conversations Project, an organization that creates constructive dialogue on divisive public issues:

- Is this question relevant to the real life and real work of the people who will be exploring it?
- Is this a genuine question—a question to which I/we really don't know the answer?
- What “work” do I want this question to do? That is, what kind of conversation, meanings, and feelings do I imagine this question will evoke in those who will be exploring it?
- Is this question likely to invite fresh thinking/feeling? Is it familiar enough to be recognizable and relevant—and different enough to call forward a new response?
- What assumptions or beliefs are embedded in the way this question is constructed?
- Is this question likely to generate hope, imagination, engagement, creative action, and new possibilities or is it likely to increase a focus on past problems and obstacles?
- Does this question leave room for new and different questions to be raised as the initial question is explored?

Powerful Questions

The following is a series of questions from the article, *The Art of Powerful Questions*, by Eric E. Vogt, Juanita Brown, and David Isaacs. They have been used by the authors and others to stimulate innovation and knowledge in a wide variety of global situations. Use them to stretch your thinking about the questions you need to stimulate innovation and knowledge in your organization.⁶

Questions for Focusing Collective Attention on Your Situation

- What question, if answered, could make the most difference to the future of (your specific situation)?
- What's important to you about (your specific situation) and why do you care?
- What draws you to this inquiry?
- What's our intention here? What's the deeper purpose (the big "why") that is really worthy of our best effort?
- What opportunities can you see in (your specific situation)?
- What do we know so far or still need to learn about (your specific situation)?
- What are the dilemmas/opportunities in (your specific situation)?
- What assumptions do we need to test or challenge here in thinking about (your specific situation)?
- What would someone who had a very different set of beliefs than we do say about (your specific situation)?

Questions for Connecting Ideas and Finding Deeper Insight

- What's taking shape? What are you hearing underneath the variety of opinions being expressed? What's in the center of the table?
- What's emerging here for you? What new connections are you making?
- What had real meaning for you from what you've heard? What surprised you? What challenged you?
- What's missing from this picture so far? What is it we're not seeing? What do we need more clarity about?
- What's been your/our major learning, insight, or discovery so far?
- What's the next level of thinking we need to do?

⁶ Source: *The Art of Powerful Questions*, Eric E. Vogt, Juanita Brown, and David Isaacs

- If there was one thing that hasn't yet been said in order to reach a deeper level of understanding/clarity, what would that be?

Questions that Create Forward Movement

- What would it take to create change on this issue?
- What could happen that would enable you/us to feel fully engaged and energized about (your specific situation)?
- What's possible here and who cares? (rather than "What's wrong here and who's responsible?")
- What needs our immediate attention going forward?
- If our success was completely guaranteed, what bold steps might we choose?
- How can we support each other in taking the next steps? What unique contribution can we each make?
- What challenges might come our way and how might we meet them?
- What conversation, if begun today, could ripple out in a way that created new possibilities for the future of (your situation)?

Meeting Design

Step One

Why are we meeting?

- Convene meeting planning team.
- Determine key purpose (desired outcomes).
- Survey meeting participants (if possible).
- Identify key topics for the agenda.
- Develop key questions to be answered for each topic.
- Which questions can be answered by:
 - Overt Knowledge—can be answered through a document or presentation
 - Tacit Knowledge—exchange of information from participants
 - New Knowledge—created by the collective interactions of participants
- Draft objectives and a high level agenda by listing the key questions in an order that makes sense.

Step Two

What process(es) will lead us to the desired outcomes?

- Create a detailed outline matching the process to be used to each key question to be answered and showing the timeframe.
- There are many different processes that can be used to accomplish the same outcome; consider the needs and preferences of the participants.
- Minimize presentation, get everyone in the room talking during the first 30 minutes to increase the likelihood of robust conversations throughout the meeting, and leave time for action planning at the conclusion of the meeting.
- Add the materials to be used, audiovisual equipment needed, and the logistical details to the detailed outline.
- Get agreement/sign-off to meeting design.

Step Three

What materials do we need?

- Create the materials needed to implement the design of the meeting (e.g., pre-reading/viewing, exercise instructions, worksheets, presentation slides, participant agenda and travel information, evaluation form, participant list, etc.)
- Provide instructions, models, or templates to help guide each person who is responsible for facilitating a specific process or delivering a segment of the meeting.

Step Four

What facilitation/presentation resources do we need?

- Select (and coach, if needed) the facilitators and presenters.

Source: Adapted from *Meetings That Matter*, Barbara Simonetti

Room Diagrams

Often overlooked, room setup can make a huge difference in the success of deliberation.⁷

U-shaped

- Large Group Discussion (up to 35 participants)
- Consensus Decision Making
- Duo & Trio Group Exercises
- Presentations

Circle

- Large Group Discussion (up to 35 participants)
- Consensus Decision Making
- Conflict Resolution Interventions
- Organization Development Interventions
- Duo & Trio Group Exercises
- Team Building Exercises

⁷ Source: *Meeting Design and Facilitation*, Charlotte Pollard

Table Groups

- Small Group Discussions
- Large Group Discussion
(if audio support is available)
- Team Exercises
- Projects
- Presentations

Theatre

- Presentations
- Duo & Trio Group Exercises

Facilitation Tips

Self-introduction

In addition to your name, professional affiliation, and business location, participants are often interested in how you see your role. They have an interest in feeling their voices will be heard, their opinions and suggestions will be respected, and their participation will be protected. So, you might include in your introduction information about your values in relation to group participation and decision-making.

Meeting Overview

Most participants appreciate knowing what to expect from the meeting. This will increase their trust in the process and their value for the results. Providing an overview shows that you are prepared, the expected outcomes are solid, and the agenda is thorough. This helps focus the participant's attention.

Your participants will want to know three things:

- *Outcomes*—What are the goals for the meeting? What do you expect to achieve? What are the results that need to be accomplished?
- *Agenda*—What are the key components of the meeting that will lead to the outcomes? What are the activities the participants can look forward to? How long will each activity take?
- *Roles*—What are the roles of the people involved, especially the facilitator, the recorder, and the participants? Are there formal roles such as chair, subject matter experts, etc.? What agreements need to be made upfront regarding the roles, their contributions, and interactions?

Ground Rules or Guidelines

Asking the group to identify several key ground rules or guidelines that will help the group work together cooperatively to achieve the outcomes helps you and the participants stay friendly and focused. Some favorite rules are:

- Be on time; start and end on time
- What is said here, stays here
- Listen, don't interrupt
- Speak concise and precise
- Allow space for others to speak
- Be hard on issues, but soft on people

- Differ respectfully
- Don't take yourself so seriously
- Misery is optional; if you don't get it, ask
- Have fun!

When you are facilitating a meeting on a complex or controversial topic, you may need to allow more free flowing conversation and dialogue. Coming to consensus will require more clarification of the issues, more reflection on the ideas, and more thoughtful decisions. The following guidelines may be helpful:

- Speak and listen with respect so we may learn from one another.
- Be as concise as possible so that others may have an opportunity to speak
- Seek clarification before making an assumption.
- Address the problem; don't attack the person.
- Protect the space for differences to be explored.
- Seek solutions that meet everyone's needs.

Time Savers⁸

There are simple ways to make the meeting more efficient, both for the facilitator and for the participants. Some favorite tips are:

- Before the meeting begins, cut off several pieces of tape for posting flipcharts. Place them along the edge of the flipchart easel or at a convenient place along the walls so you can reach them easily. This will allow you to post the flipcharts quickly and participants will probably help you with this task.
- Give each participant a tent card with their first name in big letters. Ask them to stand their tent card on end if they wish to speak. This is a clear signal to you and assures participants they will eventually be heard on the issue. It will allow participants to listen more carefully and cut down on the interruptions.

⁸ **Source:** *Meeting Design and Facilitation*, Charlotte Pollard

- If you are using the storyboarding (affinity diagramming) technique with a large group and you need the information to be more visible, use the large post it note paper that is 8" x 6" in dimension.

- Although it is beneficial to use the "round robin" response technique during a brainstorming or nominal group technique session, it can slow down the meeting if it is used too often. Once participants trust you to be inclusive, you can let the session be more freeform. The "tent card on end" technique above helps you know when someone wants to speak.

- If you are using the multi-voting technique (where participants place colored dots next to their favorite ideas), avoid using the word "vote." The word "vote" is incongruent when you are trying to reach consensus at the end. The multi-voting technique is used to show where common ground is emerging. So, let participants know that the items with the most dots indicates where common ground is forming within this particular group.

- If you are working with a recorder, either using a computer or a flipchart to capture participants' responses, it is helpful to periodically repeat the key words from a participant's response. This allows the recorder to hear the key words again and to catch up with the group if needed. However, you would not want to repeat every participant's response as this would slow the discussion down too much.

- Post one or two flipcharts off to the side of room and give them a heading called "Idea Bin" or "Parking Lot." Explain that these charts are meant to capture ideas, questions, suggestions, etc. from participants that are not central to the agenda or the desired outcomes for the meeting. This will save the ideas for future consideration, but not allow participants to go off on tangents that are not productive at the present time.

Facilitation Tips for Controversial Issues

If the issues to be addressed in a session are controversial, you can anticipate that participants will have very different points of view and be divided on how they think the issues should be addressed. In these situations, you may want to provide an opportunity for participants to voice their opinions, questions, concerns, ideas, etc. in a way that gives everyone an equal opportunity to be heard. Below are some options that can help insure that participants will feel comfortable that their individual voices will be heard.⁹

Issue Stations	Position flipchart easels and pads around the room with images and information on a specific aspect of the controversial issues. Assign a discussion leader to each station. Ask participants to visit the issue stations they want to address and work with the discussion leader to record their ideas, questions, concerns, etc. Encourage all participants to visit each station to review the information recorded.
Stenographer Station	Use a stenographer during the session to record participant messages about the issues. Participants can work with the stenographer before the session begins and during breaks. A report can be provided to the participants and to the session sponsor.
Issue Forms	Provide a form that participants can record their messages about the issues. You can also provide an electronic version of this technique by providing a link to a message board. The messages can be provided in a summary report to the session sponsor.
Hot Topic Mini-sessions	Periodically during the regular session, allow time for participants to gather in small stakeholder groups to review the new information they have heard and to consider their position in light of this new information and report out on their conclusions.
Poster Stations	Post flipchart paper on the walls of the session with issue headings. Allow time for participants to record their messages.

⁹ **Source:** Adapted from Carl Moore, The Community Store

Facilitation Aids

The following types of aids may be useful in different contexts.¹⁰

Computer Slides for Presentations

Keep in mind that your slides are the supporting act. You and the participants are the main attraction. The aids show the information that is important to remember. They also help you stay on track. The following guidelines will help you use computer projections appropriately:

- Create the slides:
 - Give each slide a heading.
 - Use key words and phrases.
 - Use dark font color on white background or white/yellow font color on blue background. Avoid using backgrounds that are too dark or cluttered with imagery.
 - Be consistent with font styles and sizes.
 - Use photos, clipart, etc.
 - Use animation sparingly and only when needed for understanding, visibility, or dramatic effect.
 - Create a handout version for participants. They can use the handout for taking notes during the meeting.
- Make arrangements with your facility contact to ensure the following are available:
 - Computer with appropriate software and means to upload the presentation file (e.g., flash drive)
 - Wireless mouse with forward/backward controls to advance the slides
 - Appropriate projector with hook-ups that are compatible with the computer
- Arrive early to test the equipment:
 - Check positioning of the projector and the screen.

¹⁰ **Source:** *Meeting Design and Facilitation*, Charlotte Pollard

- Test the sight lines from each participant’s chair.
- Make adjustments if necessary.

Flipcharts for Recording Discussions

Flipcharts are useful to record the information that results from a discussion. It keeps the discussion focused and allows everyone to see the information that is important to remember. The following guidelines will help you use flipcharts during discussions appropriately:

- Prepare for the discussion:
 - Write the questions or headings on the charts you will be using.
- During the discussion, chart participant’s responses:
 - Record everyone’s response, not just the ones you like best.
 - Record the key words and phrases of the participants; don’t translate into your words.
 - Limit the number of lines on each flipchart to 7-9.
 - Write big (e.g., 1-3 inches high).
 - Write fast to keep the momentum going, but be legible.
 - Use abbreviations.
 - If you will be using the multi-vote technique, number each item.
 - Use two different colors of markers and alternate the color of each item to make them more visible.
 - Use only dark colors, i.e., black, blue, purple, green.
 - Use lighter colors, i.e., red or orange, to highlight items, underline key words, show categories of thoughts, etc.
 - Be creative! Use drawings that illustrate key points.

Computer Worksheets for Recording Discussions

If the meeting design includes several small groups working simultaneously and if the results from each group need to be compared or consolidated into a final meeting report, it is useful to use computer worksheets and to record the information that results from the discussions electronically.

- Prepare for the discussion:
 - Develop a worksheet for each small group that lists the question(s) to be discussed.

- Use a sans serif font like Arial for best visibility.
- Test each worksheet by projecting it on a wall to ensure the left/right margins are set so they are visible even if the text is set to be viewed/zoomed at 150-200%.
- During the discussion, electronically record participant's responses:
 - Record everyone's response, not just the ones you like best.
 - Record the key words and phrases of the participants; don't translate into your words.
 - Record fast to keep the momentum going. You can correct the grammar and format later.
 - Use abbreviations. You can correct the spelling later.
 - Be familiar with common formatting techniques and keyboard shortcuts, e.g., cut, paste, bold, italic, highlight, bullets, table navigation, track changes, etc.
 - If you are working in partnership with a facilitator who is also recording on a flipchart and will be using the multi-vote technique, number each item exactly as the facilitator does.
 - Project the worksheet on a wall to be viewed/zoomed at 150-200%
 - Be prepared to scroll up/down when participants need to review the various parts of the worksheet.

Resources

Publications

The following publications offer information important to building your facilitation skills:

- **Advanced Facilitation Strategies**, Ingrid Bens, Jossey-Bass, A Wiley Imprint, San Francisco, CA, 2005.
- **A Field Guide to Good Decisions**, Mark D. Bennett and Joan McIver Gibson, Praeger Publishers, Westport, CT, 2006.
- **Extreme Facilitation**, Suzanne Ghais, Jossey-Bass, A Wiley Imprint, San Francisco, CA, 2005.
- **Facilitating Community Change**, Darvin Ayre, Gruffie Clough, and Tyler Norris, The Grove Consultants International, San Francisco, CA, 2000.
- **Facilitator's Guide to Participatory Decision-Making**, Sam Kaner, New Society Publishers, Gabriola Island, BC, 1996.
- **Flip Charts: How to Draw Them and How to Use Them**, Richard C. Brandt, University Associates, San Diego, CA, 1986.
- **Future Search**, Marvin R. Weisbord and Sandra Janoff, Berrett-Koehler Publishers, San Francisco, CA, 1995.
- **Graphic Facilitation**, David Sibbet, The Grove Consultants International, San Francisco, CA, 2006.
- **Large Group Interventions**, Barbara Benedict Bunker and Billie T. Alban, Jossey-Bass Publishers, San Francisco, CA, 1997.
- **Open Space Technology**, Harrison Owen, Abbott Publishing, Potomac, MD, 1992.
- **The Facilitator's Fieldbook**, Thomas Justice and David W. Jamieson, Ph.D., Amacom, New York, NY 1999.
- **The Change Handbook**, Peggy Holman, Tom Devane, and Steven Cady, Berrett-Koehler Publishers, San Francisco, CA, 2007.
- **The Power of Appreciative Inquiry**, Diana Whitney & Amanda Trosten-Bloom, Berrett-Koehler Publishers, Inc., San Francisco, CA, 2003.
- **The Skilled Facilitator**, Roger Schwarz, Jossey-Bass, A Wiley Imprint, San Francisco, CA, 2002.
- **The Skilled Facilitator Fieldbook**, Roger Schwarz, Jossey-Bass, A Wiley Imprint, San Francisco, CA, 2005.
- **The Technology of Participation: Group Facilitation Methods**, The Institute of Cultural Affairs, Phoenix, AZ, 1996.

- **The World Café**, Juanita Brown, Berrett Koehler Publishers, Inc., San Francisco, CA, 2005.
- **Winning Through Participation**, Laura J. Spencer, Kendall/Hunt Publishing Company, Dubuque, IA, 1989.

Organizations

The following organizations offer training in facilitation:

- Bridges of Peace, Santa Fe, NM, www.bridgesofpeace.com
- The Community Store, Santa Fe, NM, www.thecommunitystore.com
- The Grove Consultants International, San Francisco, CA, www.grove.com
- The Institute of Cultural Affairs, Phoenix, AZ, www.ica-international.org